

Research Methods and Tools – Report 2

Deliverable 2.4

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RE-DWELL

Deliverable 2.4 Research Methods and Tools – Report 2

Version 1

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Table of contents

Executive summary.....	5
1. Introduction.....	6
2. Course aims	6
3. Learning outcomes	6
4. Course structure	7
5. Learning activities	12
5.1. Session 1 (WS2, Budapest): Introduction to comparative research methodologies	12
5.2. Session 2 (online): Reflection on comparative elements in ESRs' research.....	14
5.3. Session 3 (online): Reflection on comparative elements in a EU-wide research project	15
5.4. Session 4 (Summer School 2, Valencia): Essay Workshop	16
6. Resources.....	18
7. Outputs	18
8. Course evaluation.....	20
Annex 1 – Evaluation survey.....	1

Executive summary

The purpose of this report is to document the objectives, content and implementation process of the Research Methods and Tools 2 (RMT2) course. The course is worth 4 ECTS, which is equivalent to about 100 hours of learning, including online and in-person sessions and self-directed work.

RMT2 aims to encourage ESRs to critically engage with comparative research methodologies and tools, integrating them into their research projects where appropriate. The course also reflects on the transferability of research findings outside academic context, as in the secondments.

Following feedback from other courses, the lectures were limited in number and duration and more space was given to interactive activities. Also, we used the Miro platform to provide ESRs with a curated thematic overview of comparative research methods and tools, with videos and other materials. In this way, they could watch the videos and study the materials in advance, leaving more space for online interaction and dialogue during the sessions.

The course is structured in three main tasks which are carried out throughout the course in different teaching and learning contexts:

- Task 1: Resource mapping, a group activity aimed at critically analysing existing resources (data, organisations, methodologies, methods, experts) relevant for the ESRs' research.
- Task 2: Writing an essay on selected research methods and tools, aligned with the research project
- Task 3: Peer review of an essay from another ESR

Two results of the course, an overview of qualitative and quantitative data resources and reflective essays on comparative research methodologies and tools, can be further developed. The data resources will be included as resources in the project website, and the essays are valuable research outcomes which can be further disseminated.

Participants evaluated the course through an online survey, the results of which are presented in Annex 1. The attainment of the learning aims and learning outcomes scored positive (3,9 and 3,7 out of 5 points, respectively). The RMT2 sessions during Workshop Session 2 in Budapest and the Summer School in Valencia scored 4,3 and 4,5 out of 5, respectively. The RMT2 online workshop sessions in May 2022 were not evaluated separately.

Overall, the timing of the RMT2 course on comparative methodologies and tools aligned well with the progress of the ESRs' research. This is also reflected in the evaluation of the course. It was also notable that the students mentioned the relevance of a robust theoretical underpinnings of research methodologies and tools, such as epistemological and ontological perspectives. This illustrates a deep interest among many ESR in the philosophic fundamentals of doing sound research.

1. Introduction

The purpose of this report is to document the work carried out in the course Research Methods and Tools “Comparative methodologies based on quantitative and qualitative data analysis” (RMT2): aims, learning outcomes, structure, content, learning activities, resources, and outputs.

RMT2 is the second of a three-module course focused on research methodologies and tools. RMT2 aims to increase the knowledge and capabilities of ESRs to apply and reflect on comparative methodologies based on quantitative and qualitative data analysis and to simulate ESRs to critically reflect on comparative methodologies and tools and discuss this with their peers. RMT2 received input from, and delivered input to, various RE-DWELL network activities and deliverables, notably the Budapest workshop (WS2) and the Valencia summer school 2 (SS2).

The course was prepared and delivered by Delft University of Technology (TUD). The planning of the sessions during WS2 and SS2 was discussed with the organisers of these events, the Center of Social Sciences and the Universitat Politècnica de València, respectively.

This document is structured as follows: Section 2, “Course aims”; Section 3, “Learning outcomes”; Section 4, “Course structure”; Section 5, “Learning activities”; Section 6, “Resources”; Section 7 “Outputs” and Section 8, “Evaluation”.

The evaluation survey is included in Annex 1. Participants feedback is important as their answers revealed their preferred type of learning activities, and this information can be used in the development of future courses namely RMT3.

2. Course aims

RMT2 is the second of three research and methods modules, which together aim to foster an appropriate theoretical grounding of the ESRs’ research projects in a transdisciplinary manner. RMT2 was designed for RE-DWELL purposes by TU Delft (Gerard van Bortel, Marietta Haffner, Joris Hoekstra) to assist ESRs in reflecting on comparative research methodology approaches and the application of these approaches in their own research projects.

More specifically, RMT2 has the following learning aims:

1. To introduce ESRs to the different perspectives of comparative housing research methodologies
2. To introduce ESRs to the comparative housing research landscape by creating an overview of data resources, organisations, methodologies, methods, and experts
3. To train ESR to critically reflect on various comparative research methodologies and methods and explore how these approaches can be applied to affordable and sustainable housing research in general and more specifically in the research projects of the ESRs.

3. Learning outcomes

On the successful completion of the RMT2 module, the ESRs were expected to achieve the following outcomes:

- Ability to reflect on different disciplinary perspectives to housing research
- Ability to analyse different research approaches to housing issues in terms of methods and methodological mix (comparability, transferability)
- Ability to understand and critically reflect on comparative methodologies for qualitative and quantitative research
- Ability to understand and critically reflect on the limitations of research methods
- Ability to analyse and position own research and that of another ESRs within the field of housing studies in relation to different disciplines
- Ability to understand and choose methods to suit research aims and objectives
- Ability to link social science research to the formation of housing policy; identification of multiple methods of social research, including ethnographic studies and analyses of administrative datasets

4. Course structure

RMT2 is structured in three main tasks which are carried out throughout the course in different teaching and learning contexts.

TASK 1. Resource mapping exercise (group work)

ESRs critically analysed existing resources (data, organisations, methodologies, methods, experts) relevant for their research. Task 1 incorporated the following activities:

1. Create an overview of literature and experts on different comparative methodologies and methods in housing research (e.g. GIS, Research Through Design, Ethnography) ESRs will reflect on existing publications on comparative methodologies in housing research.
2. The results of Task 1 can be collated and used to create a Who-is-Who? and What-is-What? in comparative housing research. Students developed a MIRO board to present the results of the mapping activities mentioned above.
3. For the overview of available housing-related databases (step 1 above), ESRs developed an online Excel format to submit resources. By the end of November 2022 the Excel format contained 11 entries of quantitative resources, 6 qualitative resources and 4 mixed databases.

TASK 2: Essay (individual work)

ESRs produced a max. 2,000 words essay revisiting their own research proposal, including their research questions, and integrating the different components of the RMT2 course.

TASK 3: Peer review of essay written by another ESR (individual work)

ESRs critically reflected on the essay (Task 2) of another ESR and formulated recommendations on how to improve it.

Research Methods and Tools 2 (RMT2)

Figure 1. RMT2 course structure as integrated with the network activities

Figure 1 shows the timeline for the RMT2 course, including the connections with other RE-DWELL activities.

Table 1 provides an overview of the programme structure with dates (March-November 2022) and time slots, session titles, brief content descriptions as well as the lead RE-DWELL staff. Further information is provided in Section 5 “Learning activities”.

Table 1. RMT2 session briefs

Sessions	Activities	Facilitators
	<p>RMT2 LAUNCH</p> <p>INDEPENDENT WORK: Preparation for RMT2 kick-off Workshop session.</p> <p>Assignment in preparation of Session 1</p> <p>Articles on comparative methodologies in housing research, from a pre-selected list of articles.</p>	ESRs
<p>29.3.2022</p> <p>SESSION 1</p> <p>Onsite</p> <p>Budapest workshop</p>	<p>LECTURES; INTRODUCTION TO COMPARATIVE RESEARCH METHODOLOGIES</p> <p>Lecture 1: Introduction to the RMT2 course goals, structure, planning, activities and the various individual and collective tasks for ESRs and expected deliverables</p> <p>Lecture 2: Introduction to comparative housing research methodologies</p> <p>Group work: Reflect in small groups on the studied key articles on comparative methodologies</p> <p>TASK 1: Resource mapping exercise. Introduction and group formation</p>	<p>Gerard van Bortel</p> <p>Marietta Haffner</p> <p>ESRs</p> <p>Gerard van Bortel</p>
<p>March-May 2022</p> <p>SESSION 1- (follow-up)</p> <p>Online</p>	<p>GROUP WORK</p> <p>Group work towards completion of TASK 1: Group mapping</p> <p>ESRs critically analyse the existing resources (data, organisations, methodologies, methods, experts) relevant for their research.</p>	ESRs

10.5.2022	REFLECTION ON COMPARATIVE ELEMENTS IN RESEARCH	
SESSION 2	Blended education activity: Reflection on comparative housing research methodologies using pre-recorded mini lectures ESRs had to study this material in advance.	Gerard van Bortel
SESSION 3	Interactive lecture: Reflection on comparative methodologies used in an EU-wide research project Workshop: Discuss critical elements of comparative housing research methodologies TASK 2: Essay and TASK 3: Peer review	Joris Hoekstra Gerard van Bortel
May-July 2022	INDEPENDENT WORK Preparation for Summer School 2 session: Short pitches on essay (Task 2) followed by discussion with peer-reviewers (Task 3).	ESRs
12.7.2022 SESSION 4 Onsite Valencia summer school	ESSAY WORKSHOP Presentation and discussion of essays (TASK 2) in small groups, other ESRs will act as discussants (TASK 3).	ESRs
July-Sept. 2022	INDEPENDENT & GROUP WORK Revise and submit the essay (Task 2) based on the feedback received during Summer School 2 (Task 3)	ESRs
Oct.-Nov. 2022	Fill-out online Excel format with data resources	ESRs

The course consisted of a combination of asynchronous and synchronous (online and in-person) learning opportunities. This included online lectures and workshops (group exercises, discussions and peer reviews), as well as some hybrid activities:

- A session during WS2 to kick off the course: introduction, structure, goals, activities and tasks.
- An online workshop to discuss the alignment of the various research methodologies with the research of ESRs.
- A session during SS2 where the essays written by ESRs were discussed.

All the learning events included interactive sessions for ESRs to exchange their views, share experiences and ask questions. The work done in the course accounted for 4 ECTS (100 hours) in the RE-DWELL training programme which were distributed throughout all the activities (Table 2).

Table 2. Learning type by type of activity, event and ECTS (1 ECTS = 25 hours)

Events	WS2	Online seminar (synchronous)	Online lectures (asynchronous)	SS2
Activities	Hours	Hours	Hours	Hours
F2F Lectures				
Session 1. Introduction to the RMT2 course and comparative housing research methodologies	5			
Online lectures and seminars				
Session 2. Reflection on comparative elements in ESRs' research (including pre-recorded mini-lectures)		2	5	
Session 3. Reflection on comparative methodologies in an EU-wide research project		3		
F2F Workshops				
Session 4. Comparative housing methodology workshop				5
Independent learning (80%)	20	20	20	20
Tasks 1, 2 and 3				
Total hours	25	25	25	25

5. Learning activities

RMT2 was carried out from March to November 2022 with sessions that took place in the Budapest workshop (March 2022), and in the Valencia summer school (July 2022). The sessions summarized in Table 1 are described in more detail in the following sub-sections

5.1. Session 1 (WS2, Budapest): Introduction to comparative research methodologies

This session took place during the Budapest workshop on 29 March 2022. The RMT2 kick-off session started with an introduction of the course by Gerard van Bortel (Figure 2). This was followed by an online lecture by Marietta Haffner introducing various perspectives on comparative housing research.

Figure 2. RMT2 kick-off session during the Budapest workshop

Task 1 was next introduced. It was carried out in teams and consisted of mapping a section of the comparative housing research landscape, including: resources (e.g. databases); organisations, methodologies and methods and techniques. Each of these subtasks involved identifying relevant contacts and experts.

ESRs continued in small groups to reflect on the added value of the selected articles they had studied for their own research projects. The outcomes of the groups were presented and discussed in a plenary closing session. The literature for this session was provided by the course coordinators in the form of a reading assignment and organised in these categories:

1. Views on comparative housing research from different perspectives
2. Examples of qualitative comparative cross-border research
3. Knowledge transfer

Learning aims

- To introduce ESRs to the different perspectives of comparative housing research methodologies. For this aim we used, among others, the research framework by Saunders et al., 2007¹ (Figure 3).
- To introduce ESRs to the comparative housing research landscape by creating an overview of data resources, organisations, methodologies, methods, and experts.

Figure 3. 'Research onion' (Saunders et al. 2007, adapted by author)

Learning outcomes

This session contributed to most of the RMT2 learning outcomes:

- Ability to reflect on different disciplinary perspectives to housing research
- Ability to analyse different research approaches to housing issues in terms of methods and methodological mix (comparability, transferability)
- Ability to understand and critically reflect on comparative methodologies for qualitative and quantitative research
- Ability to understand and critically reflect on the limitations of research methods
- Ability to analyse and position own research and that of another ESRs within the field of housing studies in relation to different disciplines

¹ Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2007). *Research Methods for Business Students*. 8th Edition, Financial Times Prentice Hall, Edinburgh Gate, Harlow.

5.2. Session 2 (online): Reflection on comparative elements in ESRs' research

The session took place online on 10 May 2022, in the morning. After a short introduction of the workshop aims, ESRs presented a draft framework to capture and organise the data to make a comparative housing research landscape. This was followed by a group discussion, moderated by the course coordinator, on the next steps needed to finalise this task.

ESRs addressed various comparative research methodologies in small groups based on their personal preferences. After one hour in breakout rooms, ESRs exchanged the outcomes in a plenary online session. A Miro board with mini-lectures was prepared for this task (Figure 4).

The workshop ended with an introduction of Tasks 2 and 3 and a preview of sessions 3 and 4, followed by questions and answers and ending with the session evaluation.

Figure 4. Board with mini-lectures (i.e. short videos) on research methodologies

Learning aims

- To introduce ESRs to the different perspectives of comparative housing research methodologies
- To introduce ESRs to the comparative housing research landscape by creating an overview of data resources, organisations, methodologies, methods, and experts (Task 1)
- To train ESRs to critically reflect on various comparative research methodologies and methods and explore how these approaches can be applied to affordable and sustainable housing research in general and more specifically in the research projects of the ESRs (Tasks 2 and 3)

Learning outcomes

- Ability to reflect on different disciplinary perspectives to housing research
- Ability to understand and critically reflect on comparative methodologies for qualitative and quantitative research
- Ability to understand and critically reflect on the limitations of research methods
- Ability to analyse and position own research and that of another ESRs within the field of housing studies in relation to different disciplines
- Ability to understand and choose methods appropriate to research aims and objectives

5.3. Session 3 (online): Reflection on comparative elements in a EU-wide research project

This session was carried out online on 5 May 2022, in the afternoon. Joris Hoekstra presented the methodologies and tools used in the EU-wide UPLIFT² project, which focuses on urban inequalities across European countries. The aim of the project is to explore how young people's voices can be put at the centre of youth policy in areas of housing, education and employment.

In his contribution, Joris Hoekstra addressed the challenges of doing comparative research in a multi-level setting and, in particular, the comparative analysis of in-depth interviews in 8 European cities and the application of the research results for reflexive policy-making.

Part of the afternoon workshop was dedicated to discussing ways to organize in-depth interviews in multiple countries and ensure comparability between the different countries (implications for interview guide and method of analysis).

During these sessions the next tasks to be carried out by ESRs were introduced:

² <https://uplift-youth.eu>

- Task 1 (individual). Each ESR will produce an essay (max. 2,000) critically reflecting on how different elements of RMT2 (e.g. data sources, institutions, experts, comparative methodologies and methods) are used in the ERS's individual research project. The essay should be based on the critical synthesis of the existing literature and the results of Task 1. ESRs should also reflect on how the secondments supports the comparative elements in the ESR's research.
- Task 3 (individual). Peer review of the essay (Task 2) of another ESR. Short report to be presented and discussed during Summer School 2 in July 2022.

Learning aims

- To introduce ESRs to the different perspectives of comparative housing research methodologies

Learning outcomes

- Ability to understand and critically reflect on comparative methodologies for qualitative and quantitative research
- Ability to understand and critically reflect on the limitations of research methods
- Ability to analyse and position own research and that of another ESRs within the field of housing studies in
- Ability to understand and choose methods appropriate to research aims and objectives

5.4. Session 4 (Summer School 2, Valencia): Essay Workshop

The workshop was organized during the Valencia summer school, on 12 July 2022 (Figure 5). For RMT2 the ESRs did three tasks before meeting in Valencia: a mapping exercise on comparative housing research (group work) which they had to submit on a Miro board, a reflective essay on comparative methodologies, and a peer-review of another ESR's essay.

RMT2 training activities on the topic "Comparative methodologies for qualitative and quantitative analysis" were organized in the morning session. The ESRs had to update their collaborative work on research data resources. Afterwards, there was a revision of Task 2 (Essay) and Task 3 (Peer review) in groups.

Figure 5. RMT2 sessions in Valencia summer school

Table 3 presents how the peer-review of the essays was structured in small groups. In the final plenary session, the results were discussed and the next steps were agreed upon.

Table 3. RMT2 Session 4 – Task 3 peer review

Group A	
Annette Davis	Saskia Furman
Christophe Verrier	Anna Martin
Group B	
Mahmoud Alsaeed	Marco Horvat
Zoe Tzika	Andreas Panagidis
Group C	
Tijn Croon (online)	Alex Fernández (online)
Alex Fernández	Effrosyni Roussou
Group D	
Androniki Pappa	Leonardo Ricaurte
Carolina Martín	Aya Elghandour (online)

Learning aims

- To train ESRs to critically reflect on various comparative research methodologies and methods and explore how these approaches can be applied to affordable and sustainable housing research in general and more specifically in the research projects of the ESRs.

Learning outcomes

This session was closely link to Task2 and Task3 (writing and peer-reviewing an essay) and contributed to most of the RMT2 learning outcomes, notably:

- Ability to reflect on different disciplinary perspectives to housing research
- Ability to analyse different research approaches to housing issues in terms of methods and methodological mix (comparability, transferability)
- Ability to understand and critically reflect on comparative methodologies for qualitative and quantitative research
- Ability to understand and critically reflect on the limitations of research methods
- Ability to analyse and position own research and that of another ESRs within the field of housing studies in relation to different disciplines
- Ability to understand and choose methods appropriate to research aims and objectives

- Ability to link social science research to the formation of housing policy; identification of multiple methods of social research, including ethnographic studies and analyses of administrative datasets

6. Resources

Learning was facilitated by the resources provided, mostly literature recommendations, to be used throughout the different asks. ESRs were also asked to prepare the sessions after reading the literature selectively, keeping their dissertation in mind.

The learning materials were available in Teams. The folder structure was the following:

- Course description
- Session 1 kick-off
- Session 2 online workshop (part 1)
- Session 3 online workshop (part 2)

Each of the session folders was structured as follows:

- Assignment
- Presentations
- Resources
- Task 1

To support ESRs a Miro board was developed by the course coordinators with pre-recorded mini-lectures and others resources.

7. Outputs

As described in Section 5, ESRs were to do three tasks which led to the following outputs:

Task 1 (Group work): A Miro board with an overview of methodologies and tools and an Excel spreadsheet with qualitative, quantitative and mixed databased. For the overview of available housing-related databases ESRs developed an online Excel format to submit resources. By the end of November 2022, the file contained 11 entries of quantitative resources, 6 qualitative resources and 4 mixed databases.

Task 2 (Individual work): Each ESR produced a 2,000 word essay critically reflecting on how different elements of RMT2 (e.g. data sources, institutions, experts, comparative methodologies and methods) are used in the ESR's individual research project (Table 4). The essays where based on a synthesis of the existing literature and the results of Task 1. ESRs also reflected on how the secondments supported the research methodologies discussed in the course. Most ESRs used the feedback received from their peers (Task 3) to further develop their essays.

Table 4. TASK 2: Essays

ESR	Title	
ESR1	Annette Davis	Individual research project: A reflection of comparative housing and methodologies, methods, and tools
ESR2	Saskia Furman	Research methods for investigating sustainable housing retrofit: a case for social sustainability
ESR3	Christophe Verrier	Land use and local housing regimes: what place for affordability?
ESR4	Aya Elghandour	Reflection on approaches, paradigms, and methods of research for the ESR 4 project: An integrated Life Cycle Costing framework for households' health and wellbeing
ESR5	Mahmoud Alsaeed	Exploring housing research methodologies
ESR6	Marko Horvat	Theory and application of comparative analysis in housing studies
ESR7	Anna Martin	A reflective essay
ESR8	Andreas Panagidis	'Localising' Comparative Housing Studies
ESR9	Effrosyni Roussou	Situated knowledge(s)in methods of comparative analysis in research: reflections on the importance of context and reflexivity within a globalised sustainability discourse
ESR10	Zoe Tzika	Mixed methods design for case study research of cooperative housing projects
ESR11	Tijn Croon	Energy Poverty Governance: Comparing Measurement Techniques, Alleviation Strategies and Target Efficiency of Policies
ESR12	Alex Fernández	Analysing the role of housing subsidies within the Croatian economic growth strategy: a political economy approach to SSK
ESR13	Androniki Pappa	Building a transdisciplinary (?) research methodology
ESR14	Carolina Martín	A research methodology for mass customisation of housing
ESR15	Leonardo Ricaurte	Comparative analysis of design and place-making toolkits in the UK: Methodologies to produce places that work

This is a non-limitative overview of the comparative housing research issues addressed in the essays listed above:

1. Comparing case study results from Academia (Solar Decathlon), Industry, and local government
2. Comparing energy poverty measurement techniques
3. Comparative analysis of housing systems based on a small number of cases
4. Comparing and triangulating methodologies and methods in exploratory inquiries
5. Comparative analyses of case studies (using qualitative and quantitative methods)
6. Need for a more localized scale of comparison
7. Generalisability of variables found in a single case study
8. Creating a transferable concept of housing precariat and related body of knowledge
9. Transferability of guidelines for sustainable local development through urban commons across different contexts

8. Course evaluation

ESRs evaluated the RMT2 course in three contexts: the Budapest workshop, the Valencia summer school, and a final evaluation of the course as a whole. The highlights of each evaluation are presented below. Annex 1 contains the results of the final evaluation.

Budapest workshop

The online survey for the RMT2 session in Budapest was completed by 14 ESRs and 5 supervisors/co-supervisors, showing the following results:

Question	Answers	Supervisors /Co-supervisors	ESRs	Average
Day 2 - Tuesday 29. Please evaluate "RMT2 course" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	19	4.4	4,2	4.3

Comments by ESRs based on WS2 Budapest evaluation Survey:

"It was an overall very good introductory session, the group discussion format works really well, and I believe that Gerard's willingness to adjust the course contents based on the methodologies that the ESRs (intend to) adopt in their research will be highly beneficial. I think a good addition would be to provide an overview of relevant research methodologies and map similarities, differences (e.g. phenomenology and ethnology), discuss on suitability & applicability etc."

"Great lesson! It was important that we had read a paper (so we were prepared for the discussion)! Thank you Gerard and Marietta for the great input!!"

“It is very much appreciated the effort that Gerard and Marietta are putting in trying to make the course as useful” for everyone as possible.”

“It was a very good introduction and selection of papers for understanding the comparative methodologies.”

“Openness to suggestions was great, big hopes about this course.”

“Not only was the knowledge discussed and presented. But the fact, the timing of the session was perfect since we had just started to formulate our methodology and discover the different theories and possible structures of our research methods. Also the light hands-on activity but very effective.”

“Interesting structure, but more time for discussion would be good next time.”

“I think the class will be very interesting, I think it would have been even better if everyone had been in person, but it looks good for the RMT2 class :)”

“I liked the discussion / paper task very much”

“Interesting lecture complemented by relevant literature and discussions that support the development of international comparative research strategies. A very relevant issue in our research network.”

Comments from supervisors and co-supervisors:

“We do need more different examples.”

“I think to see the presentation of them is better because you can see the problems they can have.”

“I thought the course to have been timely, useful, very well structured and enthusiastically engaged by the ESRs.”

Valencia summer school

Fifteen participants evaluated the RMT2 session during the summer school in Valencia through an anonymous online survey. For the RMT2 session on 12 July, the 15 available responses averaged 4.5 out of 5 points.

Question	Answers	Average
Please evaluate Research Methodologies and Tools session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	15	4.5

Some of the positive feedback referred to:

“understand the position of all of the ESRs and to know more about their own research”

“get ‘in-depth feedback’ and specified “other ESR and supervisors feedback”

“also hear everyone else’s peer review ... Very useful and relevant”

A positive summary comment was stated as follows:

“Both the ESR’s peer-review presentations and the discussions were of high quality and have helped create links within the network and improve ESR’s research. The learning aims of the session have been met.”

The negative comments related to not receiving more detailed guidelines about the purpose and the content of the exercises and about getting acquainted with specific research methods. One ESR doubted the learning of the task:

“All in all, I’m not sure I learned how to do a peer-review after this session”, while another found that “some peer review of other ESRs sounds aggressive and I did not like that”.

Regarding the “RMT2 Course: Comparative methodologies based on quantitative and qualitative data analysis” session, the rating was mostly positive but there were different opinions. Relevant comments:

“Very useful! Peer-reviews among us is a great way to have feedback!”.

“In order for a successful and meaningful peer review to take place, we need to either be actual peers, as in share the same educational background, or build a foundation, a common ground on which to facilitate communication and understanding between the different disciplines involved in this project.

“In general well organised but could be improved by adding some examples of other person’s research and how they used research methods. Peer review content is not always about methods... can at times drift toward theory instead of methodologies.”

Overall course evaluation

RMT2 was evaluated by 10 ESRs through an anonymous online survey. The aim was to evaluate the attainment of the learning aims and outcomes, and to identify areas needing improvements to inform the development of RMT2 and RMT3. Annex 1 contains the full survey and responses,

Annex 1 – Evaluation survey

This annex contains the questions and answers to the RMT2 evaluation survey.

COURSE LEARNING AIMS

Based on 10 responses of ESRs

1. Please indicate to what extent the learning aims of the RMT2 course have been achieved

(from 1-not achieved at all to 5-fully achieved).

[More Details](#)

■ 1 ■ 2 ■ 3 ■ 4 ■ 5

Introduce you to the different perspectives of comparative housing research methodologies and...

Introduce you to the comparative housing research landscape (e.g. data resources, organisations,...

Train you to critically reflect on various comparative research methodologies and tools.

Explore how these approaches can be applied to affordable and sustainable housing research in...

Explore how these approaches can be applied to your research project.

Comments:

“The course was very helpful in introducing different research methodologies and how to carry out comparative research which I could better grasp by applying/choosing which methods to apply to my own research project. It also helped to peer review and discuss the other ESRs work to learn about other research methods and consolidate the learning”.

“In terms of theoretical background and resources, a good and in-depth overview was given, but I personally feel that I lack a lot in even more basic skills, e.g. how to construct a successful survey, or how to conduct an interview in a way that is as unbiased as possible, how to pick and formulate the questions etc. Also, how to quantitatively analyse data, given that I have next to zero knowledge of statistics. I feel that in general it has been assumed that we all possess these relevant skills, but after some discussions with my colleagues, I realised that a lot of us are missing such skills. Maybe we could organise sessions (either as part of RMT3 or as free-standing seminars) where we draw from the large pool of expertise within Re-Dwell, i.e. our supervisors & partners?”

“The multiple teaching methods used in the course made the learning experience on comparative methodologies very rich and engaging. From lectures and literature; to workshops and hands-on activities; to writing and group work, we had the chance to explore and reflect on our personal research methods, also learning a lot from each other”.

“It was a comprehensive overview of comparative research approaches. Prof. Gerard and the guest speakers offer diverse and insightful information about research projects they are conducting or have conducted. Although I am not using this type of methodology in my project, I am more confident to embark on such an endeavour in the future”.

LEARNING OUTCOMES

Based on 8 responses by ESRs

3. Please indicate to what extent the RMT2 learning outcomes have been achieved

(from 1-not achieved at all to 5-fully achieved).

[More Details](#)

Comments:

“I am sad we did not receive feedback from professors on our essays. It would be helpful to comment on it to assure us if we understand research approaches properly or not. The videos and links Gerard shared with us on the Miro board were very helpful”.

“It was definitely an amazing opportunity to be introduced to all these concepts. The major output for me was to start forming an understanding on what research is about. Of course, given the time constraints, some topics were discussed less than others, but I believe we made the best use of the time we had. Thank you to the course coordinators for the great organisation”.

“The essay and interactive activities with other colleagues were a great opportunity to analyse, reflect and share thoughts and ideas about conducting research in our field”.

Suggestions to improve the RMT2 course in future to better attain the learning aims and outcomes

“I’m very satisfied with the course it would be helpful to revisit our methodologies as these become more defined in our projects and re-present why these were chosen above other methods. It would be good to get feedback and rigorously test our research design”.

“More interactive workshops, more hands-on activities”

“I would personally be more keen to submitting our methodology and methods in the form of a detailed research diagram (corresponding/creating links to our specific questions etc.) instead of an essay, in order to make it easier for all of us to look at each other’s work. Doing so, these personal diagrams would differentiate from the common diagram that we created by giving some more condensed details on our research.”

“All Miro boards, any task and all the presentations need to be organized in the RMT folder on Teams. It was confusing to find the right document when I need it”.

“A more intensive and collected number of sessions over two-three weeks only on research methods (similar to masters course structure) would be much more useful but this is related to the way the Re-dwell programme was structured in general. I think it is flawed in this respect as it does not allow in depth learning due to quite a lot of jumping around, both in terms of locations and topics”.

“The course was very well taught. I really enjoyed the peer review exercise as it allowed us to have in-depth and insightful conversations in smaller groups around specific common interests or topics. Something I felt could not be achieved when feedback was given in a more formal presentation”.

Suggestions for the Research Methodologies and Tools (RMT3) course on Transferring research findings to community stakeholders (according to research proposal).

“Discuss tools and methods on conducting interviews and focus groups, as well as tips in constructing surveys that are not biased and efficient. Also look at methods and - possibly digital- tools of analysing the results of surveys and interviews. It will be valuable to collect a repository of analysis tools and open software”.

“I would like to look into different software that can be used to better process and analyse the data collected. Something that could also be useful, more practical and adapted to the phase of our research project”.

“Open discussion with local people on a specific subject that concerns both researchers and non-academic stakeholders is perhaps more realistic than transferring knowledge from expert to non-expert”.

“To have more examples to be shared with us. I would like to have a reading list to get back to, in a folder on Teams”.